

Call for Chapters and Contributions

Reprisals against integrity

Retaliation against those who expose systemic harm

Edited volume with Open Book Publishers. International conference under the EU COST Action BEACON CA24106.

This call invites contributions to a high level international edited volume addressing reprisals against those who document systemic harm across health systems, science, academia, environmental governance, and related domains.

The project is coordinated within the EU COST Action BEACON, a large international research network working on One Health, open science, research integrity, and institutional accountability. The volume will be published open access with Open Book Publishers, a leading scholar led, non profit press operating under a diamond open access model, with no publication fees for authors.

Scope

We seek empirically grounded contributions documenting and analysing reprisals such as

- 1 Administrative sanctions
- 2 Legal harassment
- 3 Professional exclusion
- 4 Reputational attacks
- 5 Threats to safety

Across contexts including health care, public health, environmental science, academia, governance, and related fields.

The volume adopts a One Health perspective and focuses on verifiable evidence. Speculative or unsubstantiated claims are not considered.

Who can contribute

- 1 Researchers and academics
- 2 Health professionals and practitioners
- 3 Citizen scientists and community based experts
- 4 Investigative journalists
- 5 Affected individuals and populations

Interdisciplinary and co authored work is encouraged. Support from the COST Action is available to facilitate collaboration and methodological strengthening where needed.

Key features

- 1 No publication fees
- 2 No conference or participation fees
- 3 Open access publication
- 4 Transparent open peer review starting late 2026
- 5 Integration within an EU funded scientific network

All activities are free of charge for authors, speakers, attendees, and readers.

Contributors may access COST Action funding mechanisms, including Short Term Scientific Missions of up to 4,000 euros, to support research and collaboration.

Process

Submissions are evaluated on a rolling basis and developed into full chapters through an open, transparent peer review process under strict open science and ethical principles.

Key dates

- 1 Rolling submission and review process throughout 2026 and 2027
- 2 Book publication by late 2027
- 3 Online international conference immediately following publication, focused on dissemination and awareness
- 4 Authors will participate as speakers in the conference

Submission

Send proposals including title, abstract, methods, and ethical considerations to garcia.henning@health.int.eu.org.

Selective process. Empirical rigor and ethical integrity are required.